

Digital Self-Presentation and Online Personnel of Very Dark Man

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15873069>

Abstract

The advent of social media has transformed the way individuals present themselves online, giving rise to the concept of digital self-presentation. This study explored the relationship between digital self-presentation and online persona, with a specific focus on the Very Dark Man (VDM) phenomenon. Using a descriptive survey method, this study collected data from 385 online participants who self-identified as VDM enthusiasts. The results showed that VDM engages in strategic digital self-presentation to curate an online persona that reflects his idealised self. The findings revealed that this digital self-presentation is characterised by a fascination with darkness, mystery and intellectualism. The findings also suggested that online *persona* is a critical aspect of digital self-presentation, as VDM uses online platforms to experiment with different identities and *personas* as viewed by the enthusiasts. Thus, since Very Darkman's engagement with trending topics enhances his visibility, he should diversify his content strategy to maintain audience interest. This can include a mix of informative, entertaining and interactive content to sustain engagement beyond viral discussions.

Keywords: Digital Self-Presentation, Online Personnel, Very Dark Man (Vdm), Social Media, Descriptive Survey Method

Introduction

The internet has changed how people show themselves to others. Digital self-presentation is how people choose to share their personal image online, especially on social media and professional websites. In today's world, people use these online spaces to create a certain image of themselves for social, work, or personal reasons. One of such persons who have taken huge advantage of the internet to create a digital presence for themselves is Very Dark Man.

According to Goffman (1959) in Mehdizadeh (2010), self-presentation is like a performance where people adjust their behaviour depending on who is watching. In the digital world, this process has become even more complex because individuals now manage their identities across multiple online platforms, each with different audiences and expectations. For example, a person may present themselves as professional and

serious on LinkedIn while being more casual and humorous on Twitter or Instagram. This requires careful control over what they post, how they interact with others, and how they respond to feedback. Social media also allows for selective self-presentation, where individuals highlight their achievements, positive experiences, and desirable traits while hiding aspects that may not fit their preferred image.

Ellison *et al* (2006) explain that a major part of digital self-presentation is selecting what to share. Many people on social media highlight their achievements, talents and experiences while hiding things they think are less impressive. This is because they want approval and validation from others. Additionally, digital self-presentation is influenced by social validation, as people seek likes, comments and shares to reinforce their online identity. As noted by the authors, maintaining different personas across platforms can be stressful, most especially when public perception changes or when past posts resurface. This shows that while digital self-presentation provides opportunities for self-expression, it also comes with challenges related to authenticity, reputation management, and social pressure.

Walther *et al* (2008) assert that many online personalities face criticism, cyberbullying and misinterpretation of their words. Research shows that people who present themselves boldly online often attract both admiration and backlash, making it difficult to maintain a consistent online image while facing public scrutiny. Those who express strong opinions, challenge popular beliefs, or display confidence tend to gain a loyal following of supporters who appreciate their honesty and courage. However, at the same time, they also receive criticism, negative comments, or even online attacks from those who disagree with them. Social media amplify both praise and criticism, as posts can spread quickly and reach a large audience. This means that every action, statement, or even past behaviour can be closely examined and judged. For some, this pressure leads to self-censorship, where they carefully filter their words and actions to avoid controversy. Others, however, embrace the attention, using it to strengthen their influence or shape public debates.

Another issue with digital self-presentation is the constant pressure to maintain a perfect image. Many online influencers feel the need to stay relevant by regularly engaging with their audience and keeping up with the latest trends. This means they must frequently update their social media profiles, create new content, and carefully manage their public image. The fear of losing followers or being seen as outdated pushes them to remain active online, often at the cost of their mental well-being.

In Nigeria today, one popular social media personality who understands digital self-presentation is Very Dark Man. He is known for speaking boldly about social issues and fighting for justice. Using platforms like TikTok, Instagram and Twitter, he presents himself as a fearless activist who is not afraid to challenge people in power. His style includes direct and unfiltered speech, which makes him stand out. He also knows how to engage with trending topics, which helps him stay relevant and attract more followers. However, while digital self-presentation can be a powerful tool for influence and activism,

it also comes with risks. Many influencers, including Very Dark Man, have faced criticism for their statements or actions. The internet never forgets, and old posts can be brought back to question a person's credibility. This makes it important for social media personalities to carefully manage their online reputation. As a result of these challenges, studying how people like Very Dark Man handle digital self-presentation can help us understand the benefits and dangers of maintaining a strong online image.

In the age of social media, online personas can shape public opinion, influence social change and affect personal and professional opportunities. However, maintaining a digital self-presentation is challenging when dealing with criticism, misinformation, and the pressures of public attention. The case of Very Dark Man highlights these challenges, as he constantly engages in social discourse while managing his online identity. While his digital self-presentation has earned him a strong following, it has also subjected him to controversy and attacks. Against this backdrop, the problem this study sought to investigate is the digital self-presentation Very Dark Man and how does this impact his persona.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Explore how Very Darkman presents himself online.
2. Find out the effects of social media algorithms on Very Darkman self-presentation and persona.
3. Ascertain the impact of Very Darkman digital self-presentation on his persona and public life.

Theoretical Framework

The researchers adopted the dramaturgical theory which was developed by Erving Goffman in 1959. The theory explains how people present themselves in everyday life as if they were actors on a stage. According to Goffman, individuals carefully control their behaviour based on their audience, just like actors adjust their performance depending on the scene. This means that people change how they act, speak and appear, depending on where they are and who is watching. In real life, we act differently at work, at home, or with friends. In the digital world, this becomes even more complex because social media allows people to present different versions of themselves to a large audience.

The theory has key tenets that explain self-presentation. One of these is the front stage and back stage behaviour. The front stage is where people carefully craft their image for the public, just like a performer on stage. The back stage is where they can be their true selves without worrying about others' opinions. Another important idea in the theory is impression management, where people try to control how others see them by choosing what to share and what to hide. On social media, influencers and online personalities, like Very Dark Man, carefully manage their posts, comments and appearances to shape their online identity.

This theory is appropriate for this study because digital self-presentation works in the same way as Goffman's idea of performance. Online, people actively control how they are seen by selecting what content to post, how to interact with followers, and how to respond to criticism. Influencers like Very Dark Man use different strategies to appear confident, bold and outspoken. However, just like in real life, the more people watch, the more they judge and this can lead to both praise and backlash. This study examines how digital self-presentation affects influencers and how they manage their online identity.

The relevance of the theory is clear in today's digital world, where people perform different roles across various social media platforms. Just as Goffman suggested, social media users present a carefully curated version of themselves, which might not always reflect their true personality. The theory helps explain why influencers put so much effort into maintaining their online presence and why they face pressure to remain consistent. It also shows why public figures can struggle with criticism and the long-term effects of past statements resurfacing. By using Goffman's dramaturgical theory, this study will better understand the challenges of digital self-presentation and how it shapes online identities.

The Very Darkman

Martins Vincent Otse, who is widely known as VeryDarkMan is a Nigerian activist, critic and social media influencer born on April 8, 1994, in Edo State, Nigeria. He grew up in Kaduna, Nigeria. Otse gained mainstream attention in 2022 following his associations with Nigerian celebrities. He gained more attention after uploading controversial videos on his social media handle, most especially on Instagram. In June 2023, Nigerian singer Davido followed him on Instagram and publicly endorsed him. Otse was subsequently nominated for Silverbird's Most Influential Social Media Influencer of the Year award, (Verydarkblackman, 2024).

On platforms like TikTok, Instagram and Twitter, VeryDarkMan employs distinct self-presentation strategies to engage his audience. On Instagram, he describes himself as an "Online police not an activist," emphasising his role in scrutinising societal issues. His content often features direct critiques and discussions on trending topics, aiming to provoke thought and action among his followers. This approach aligns with self-presentation theories, where individuals use verbal and non-verbal cues to project a particular image in society, (Open Newcastle, 2024).

Public perception of VeryDarkMan is polarised. While many appreciate his boldness in addressing controversial topics, others criticise his methods, leading to legal challenges. In March 2024, he was arrested on allegations of cyberbullying and cyberstalking, including false accusations against Nigerian actresses and officials. He pleaded not guilty and was remanded in police custody until his hearing on May 29, 2024. After two weeks in detention, he was released. In June 2024, he was arrested again at his Abuja residence on defamation charges related to a social media exposé. Otse was questioned by police on June 30, 2024, regarding defamation allegations and released

shortly after. No arrest was made, contrary to initial reports. These incidents highlight the complex dynamics between online self-presentation, public reception, and legal implications in the digital age.

Conceptualising Digital Self-Presentation

Goffman (1959) defined self-presentation as the way individuals consciously or unconsciously control how they are perceived by others, comparing it to a theatrical performance where people act differently based on their audience. In the digital age, this means individuals develop their online personas and decide what aspects of their lives to share to create a desired impress. Ellison, Heino & Gibbs (2006) described digital self-presentation as a strategic process where individuals selectively share information online to shape their identity and attract social or professional connections. They noted that online users often edit photos, modify personal descriptions, and carefully frame their interactions to align with social expectations.

Chou & Edge (2012) argued that digital self-presentation involves presenting an idealised version of oneself on social media, usually emphasising positive experiences while downplaying struggles. This, they noted, creates a distorted reality where individuals compare themselves to unrealistic portrayals, affecting self-esteem and mental well-being. When individuals repeatedly see polished and idealised versions of their peers online, they may feel pressure to maintain a similar image, leading to stress and dissatisfaction. This also shows the potential risks of digital self-presentation, where authenticity can be compromised in favour of maintaining an appealing online presence. In another study, Chou & Edge (2012) argued that this pressure can lead to stress and burnout, leaving influencers feeling exhausted, unhappy or insecure. The need to always appear successful and flawless can also make them compare themselves to others, further increasing feelings of anxiety. In extreme cases, some influencers struggle with self-worth, as their confidence becomes tied to likes, comments, and online approval.

From the above definitions, it can be deduced that digital self-presentation refers to the way people manage their identities and image on online platforms such as social media, websites and professional networks. With the rise of the internet, individuals now have greater control over how they present themselves to the world. They choose what to share, what to hide and how to interact with others to shape their digital identity. This has become important for influencers, public figures and professionals who rely on their online presence to connect with their audience. Chou & Edge (2012) outlined the following as key features of digital self presentation:

- a. **Selectivity:** Unlike face-to-face interactions where people's expressions and emotions are visible in real-time, the online space allows individuals to edit and refine their content. People can choose the best photos, write carefully crafted captions, and delete posts that do not align with their desired image. This selective

sharing enables individuals to present an ideal version of themselves, but it also raises concerns about authenticity.

- b. **Adaptability:** Different social media platforms require different forms of self-presentation. On LinkedIn, users present a professional identity, highlighting their achievements, skills, and work experience. On Instagram or TikTok, self-presentation may focus more on lifestyle, fashion, or entertainment. People adapt their digital personas depending on the expectations of each platform, ensuring that they engage effectively with their intended audience.

Challenges of Digital Self-Presentation

Digital self-presentation allows people to control how they are seen online, but it also comes with several challenges. The internet gives individuals the power to choose what they share, but this can create problems when people feel pressured to present only the best parts of their lives. While self-presentation can help build personal and professional connections, it can also lead to stress, misunderstandings and other negative effects. Vogue (2025); Wan & Lu (2023) identified the following as major challenges of digital self presentation:

- a. **Authenticity:** One major challenge is maintaining authenticity. Many people feel the need to create a perfect image of themselves online. They carefully select their pictures, edit their posts, and filter their content to look more successful or happy than they actually are. This can make it hard to be truly honest about personal struggles or real-life challenges. When people try too hard to look perfect, they may feel disconnected from their true selves, leading to feelings of emptiness or insecurity.
- b. **Comparison:** Another issue is social comparison. When people see others posting pictures of vacations, expensive items, or exciting experiences, they may start comparing their lives to these online images. This can create feelings of jealousy or low self-esteem, especially if someone believes their own life is not as interesting or successful. The problem is that most people only share their best moments online, not their struggles or failures, which can give a false idea of reality.
- c. **Online backlash and criticism** are also major challenges. People who share their opinions, achievements or personal experiences online may face harsh comments or negative reactions from others. Public figures, influencers, and even regular social media users can be criticised for their posts, sometimes leading to online bullying or "cancel culture." This makes digital self-presentation risky, as one wrong post can damage a person's reputation or mental well-being.
- d. **Another challenge is privacy concerns.** The more people share online, the more they risk exposing personal information to strangers, hackers, or even companies that use

data for advertising. Some individuals have faced issues where their private pictures or messages were leaked, causing embarrassment or harm. Maintaining a balance between sharing and protecting personal information is difficult with the increasing use of technology in daily life.

e. Mental health effects are also a serious issue. Constantly managing an online image can be exhausting. Influencers and content creators, for example, often feel pressure to keep posting content to stay relevant. This can lead to stress, anxiety and even burnout. The need to always look good, be entertaining, or meet audience expectations can take a toll on a person's well-being. Studies have shown that excessive social media use can contribute to depression and self-doubt.

f. Another problem is misinterpretation of online content. When people communicate face-to-face, they use facial expressions, voice tones, and body language to convey meaning. However, online posts, texts and comments can be easily misunderstood because they lack these cues. A joke might be taken as an insult or a simple statement might seem offensive. This can lead to conflicts or damage relationships, making digital communication more complicated than real-life conversations.

g. Balancing multiple online identities can be challenging. Many people have different social media accounts for personal, professional, or social purposes. They may act differently on LinkedIn compared to Instagram or TikTok. Managing these different personas while staying true to oneself can be difficult. It can also be stressful to maintain consistency across different platforms without feeling overwhelmed.

Role of Social Media in Shaping Online Personas

Social media play a major role in how people create and manage their online identities. With platforms like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok and Twitter, individuals can carefully shape how they want to be seen by others. According to Goffman (1959) in Mehdizah (2010), self-presentation is like a performance where people adjust their behaviour based on their audience. In the digital world, this means choosing profile pictures, writing bios, and posting content that reflect a certain image. Social media allows users to highlight positive aspects of their lives while hiding things they do not want others to see. This ability to control information makes online personas different from real-life identities.

Fardouly *et al* (2015) explain that one of the key ways social media shapes online personas is through curated content. People tend to post their happiest moments, achievements, and attractive pictures to create a positive image of themselves. This selective sharing can lead to what Chou & Edge (2012) call the "idealised self," where people appear more successful or happy than they actually are. Studies have shown that this can influence how others see them and how they see themselves. Constantly

maintaining an idealised image can lead to pressure and even anxiety, as individuals feel the need to live up to their online personas.

Another way social media influences self-presentation is through audience feedback. Likes, comments and shares act as validation, encouraging people to continue posting certain types of content. According to Leary & Kowalski (1990), self-presentation is driven by both personal goals and audience reactions. If a post receives a lot of positive engagement, the user is likely to repeat that behaviour. On the other hand, negative comments or lack of engagement may cause them to change their online persona. This feedback loop shapes how people present themselves over time, often leading them to adopt more socially accepted behaviours.

Additionally, the rise of influencers has changed how people approach online self-presentation. Social media personalities, like Very Dark Man in Nigeria, have mastered the art of digital self-presentation to gain followers and influence public opinion. They carefully craft their content, engage with trending topics and interact with audiences in ways that boost their popularity. However, this also comes with risks, such as backlash or the resurfacing of old posts that can harm their reputation (Marwick & Boyd, 2011). Kaplan and Haenelin (2010) points out social media algorithms also play a role in shaping online personas. These platforms show users content that matches their interests, reinforcing certain behaviours and identity traits. If someone frequently posts about fitness, for example, they may see more fitness-related content and feel encouraged to continue presenting themselves as a health-conscious person. This digital reinforcement shapes how people define themselves over time, sometimes even influencing their real-life behaviours.

Empirical Review

Ellison, Heino & Gibbs (2006) examined how individuals manage their self-presentation on online dating platforms. The study aimed to examine how individuals manage their self-presentation on online dating platforms. It focused on understanding how users selectively present themselves to attract potential partners while maintaining credibility. The researchers conducted qualitative interviews with online dating users to explore their strategies for self-presentation. They analysed how individuals curate their profiles and engage in communication to create a favourable impression. The study found that people carefully curate their online profiles by choosing attractive photos, editing personal details, and using strategic communication to create a favourable impression. However, the research also highlighted the challenge of authenticity vs. idealisation, where users struggle to balance presenting their best selves while remaining truthful. This study relates to the above study in terms online persona, while the above study used interviews to generate data, the current study rest on survey.

Chou & Edge (2012) explored the relationship between self-presentation on social media and its psychological effects on users. This study aimed to explore the relationship between social media self-presentation and its psychological effects on users. It

investigated how social media comparisons influence individuals' self-esteem and mental well-being. The researchers conducted a survey-based study with social media users, analysing how exposure to curated online content affects personal emotions and self-perception. The study examined how frequently individuals compared themselves to others online. The research found that individuals who frequently compare themselves to others online often experience lower self-esteem and increased anxiety. The study revealed that people tend to post only the best parts of their lives, creating a false reality that can make others feel inadequate. The study differs from the current study in that the reviewed study examined the psychological effect of online curated persona on emotions. This study rather looks at how Very Dark presents himself and the impact on his persona as viewed by social media users in Benin City.

Methodology

The researchers adopted a descriptive survey research design to gather data. A total of 385 copies of the questionnaire were directly distributed to residents of Benin City, which has a population of approximately 2,045,000 million, according to the city population (2024). To derive the sample, Australian sample size calculator was used. Respondents were selected based on the stratified, purposive and systematic sampling techniques. The researcher adopted the structure of the three dominant local governments in Benin City; that is Oredo, Ikpoba-Okha and Egor Local governments as strata, then, purposive sampling was used to select four popular communities in each local government. The systematic random sampling technique was used to select the K^h house in each road and the instrument was administered in such houses until saturation point was reached. In Egor, the selected roads were technical road, textile mill road, Uwelu road and medical store road. That of oredo include Siloko, Ekewan, Second and Mission Roads. In Ikpoba-Okha; Lucky way, Agbor Road, St Saviour and Upper Sakponba were selected. They were selected based on their popularity and the selected respondents were individuals with strong social media usage. The collected data were organised into tables and analysed using average mean. Since a four point likert scale was used, A mean benchmark of 2.50 was used to determine whether respondents agreed or disagreed with each statement.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table1: Very Darkman and Online Persona

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
Very Darkman strategically engages with trending topics to enhance his visibility.	300	75	0	0	3.75	Agree
He effectively manages online criticism and controversies.	220	111	20	8	3.59	Agree
Very Darkman self-presentation differs significantly across TikTok, Instagram, and Twitter.	40	45	100	25	2.05	Disagree

Average mean 3.13 Agree

Based on the data presented in table 1, it is clear that Very Darkman effectively manages his online persona through strategic engagement with trending topics, as indicated by a high mean score of 3.75. This shows that his ability to stay relevant by discussing popular issues contributes significantly to his visibility on social media. Additionally, the data reveal that he is relatively successful in handling online criticism and controversies, with a mean score of 3.59. This implies that his approach to addressing public reactions helps maintain his influence and credibility. However, the responses indicate that his self-presentation does not vary significantly across different social media platforms, with a mean score of 2.05, indicating a consistent digital persona rather than platform-specific adaptations.

With an average mean of 3.13, the findings confirm that Very Darkman effectively manages his online presence. His strategic engagement and crisis management skills contribute to his sustained relevance and audience engagement.

Table 2: Social Media Algorithms promotes Very Darkman’s Visibility

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
The type of content he posts affects how much engagement he receives.	244	117	0	0	3.61	Agree
Very Darkman’s popularity is strongly influenced by the way social media platforms promote his content.	140	180	10	0	3.30	Agree
Social media algorithms significantly influence the visibility of Very Darkman’s content.	200	120	16	2	3.38	Agree
Average mean					3.43	Agree

Based on the data in table 2, it is evident that social media algorithms play a crucial role in shaping Very Darkman’s visibility online. The findings indicate that the type of content he posts directly affects his engagement levels, with a high mean score of 3.61. This shows that his ability to attract attention depends largely on the nature of his posts, highlighting the importance of content strategy in maintaining online influence. Additionally, the data reveal that social media platforms significantly influence his popularity through content promotion, as reflected in a mean score of 3.30. This implies that platform algorithms determine how widely his posts reach audiences, reinforcing the idea that visibility is not solely dependent on content but also on how platforms distribute it. Furthermore, with a mean score of 3.38, the data confirm that social media algorithms play a major role in determining how often and to whom his content is shown. With an

overall average mean of 3.43, the findings showed that Very Darkman’s visibility is largely shaped by social media algorithms. While engaging content is essential, platform algorithms ultimately determine how much exposure he gets.

Table 3: Impact of Very Darkman’s Digital Self-Presentation on his Persona and Public Life

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
Public perception of Very Darkman is shaped by his self-presentation on social media.	112	216	0	0	3.28	Agree
His online activities have affected his real-life reputation and opportunities.	100	210	20	0	3.30	Agree
Very Darkman’s self-presentation helps him connect better with his audience	124	180	24	0	3.24	Agree
Average mean					3.29	Agree

Based on the data in table 3, it is clear that Very Darkman’s digital self-presentation significantly impacts both his personal and public life. The findings show that public perception of him is strongly influenced by how he presents himself on social media, with a mean score of 3.28. This shows that his online persona shapes how people view him, reinforcing the idea that social media presence plays a key role in building an individual’s image. Furthermore, the study revealed that his online activities have real-life consequences, affecting his reputation and opportunities, as reflected in the mean score of 3.30. This highlights the link between digital identity and offline life, showing that online actions can have lasting effects beyond social media platforms. Additionally, the data indicates that his self-presentation helps him connect better with his audience, with a mean score of 3.24. This shows that his strategic online image strengthens his relationship with followers, making him more relatable and engaging.

With an overall average mean of 3.29, the findings confirm that Very Darkman’s digital self-presentation plays a crucial role in shaping his real-life experiences. While his online persona boosts engagement and visibility, it also influences public perception and has direct implications on his personal and professional life.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 was used to answer the research question on how Very Darkman manages his online persona. The findings revealed that social media play a significant role in shaping his digital identity, as indicated by a high mean score of 3.75 for his engagement with trending topics. This shows that he strategically aligns his content with viral discussions to enhance his visibility and maintain relevance. However, social media also present challenges, such as managing online criticism and controversies (3.59), which require constant effort to uphold his reputation. Additionally, the data showed that his self-presentation remains largely uniform across different platforms (2.05), indicating a

consistent brand image rather than platform-specific adaptations. These findings align with Goffman's (1959) theory of self-presentation, which posits that individuals curate their public personas to control audience perception. Similarly, Marwick & Boyd (2011) argue that digital influencers must navigate "context collapse," ensuring that their content resonates across diverse audiences. Very Darkman's reliance on trending topics and his ability to handle criticism demonstrate his understanding of digital audience dynamics.

Table 2 provided answers to the research question on how social media algorithms influence Very Darkman's visibility. The findings indicate that his content type significantly affects engagement levels, as reflected by a mean score of 3.61. This shows that algorithmic preferences determine which of his posts gain traction, emphasising the need for strategic content creation. Additionally, the role of platform algorithms in boosting his visibility was notable, with a mean score of 3.30, highlighting the dependency of online influencers on social media systems to reach broader audiences. The influence of algorithms on his visibility was also high (3.38), confirming that digital exposure is largely dictated by platform-specific ranking mechanisms. These findings align with DeVito (2017), who highlights that algorithmic curation dictates content reach and engagement. Similarly, Gillespie (2014) argues that social media platforms act as gatekeepers, determining which posts gain prominence.

Table 3 was used to answer the research question on how Very Darkman's online self-presentation affects his public and personal life. The findings revealed that public perception of him is significantly shaped by his social media presence, with a mean score of 3.28. This indicates that his digital persona influences how audiences and stakeholders view him. Additionally, the findings showed that his online activities impact his real-life reputation and opportunities (3.30), reinforcing the idea that digital identities extend beyond virtual spaces. Furthermore, the data highlighted that his self-presentation enables better audience connection (3.24), indicating that digital authenticity fosters engagement and loyalty. These findings align with Van Dijck (2013) who argues that online personas have tangible real-world effects on professional and personal interactions. Similarly, Hogan (2010) emphasises that digital self-presentation is not merely about visibility, but also about relationship-building. The study confirms that while social media provide opportunities for reputation enhancement, they also pose risks that require careful navigation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusively, it can be deduced that Very Darkman strategically manages his online persona through engagement with trending topics and effective reputation management. However, social media present challenges, such as the need to navigate criticism and maintain a consistent identity. Additionally, social media algorithms play a crucial role in shaping his visibility, reinforcing the importance of understanding platform dynamics. Finally, his digital self-presentation significantly impacts both his personal and public life, shaping audience perceptions, career opportunities, and social interactions. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were given:

1. Since Very Darkman's engagement with trending topics enhances his visibility, he should diversify his content strategy to maintain audience interest. This can

- include a mix of informative, entertaining and interactive content to sustain engagement beyond viral discussions.
2. Given that managing online criticism and controversies is a key challenge, Very Darkman should develop a structured approach to handling negative feedback
 3. Since social media algorithms play a significant role in his visibility, Very Darkman should continuously analyse algorithmic trends and update his content strategy accordingly.
 4. Given that his self-presentation helps him connect better with his audience, he should maintain a balance between professional branding and authenticity.

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